

FORMATION OF INITIAL CONCEPTS OF THE CONCEPT OF SPACE IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract : This in the article initial class in their students space to the concept about initial concepts explanation their ways analysis light up passed .

Key words : artistic work , image , space concept , literary place

Abstract: In this article, the ways of explaining the initial concepts of the concept of space in primary school students, their analysis is highlighted.

Key words: artistic work, image, concept of space, literary space.

Annotation: V dannoy state osveshcheny sposoby ob'yasneniya iskhodnykh ponyatiy ponyatiya prostranstva u mladshikh shkolnikov, ix analysis.

Klyuchevye slova: khudojestvennoe proizvedenie, obraz, concept prostanstva, literaturnoe prostanstvo.

Get started education in the system start ' drink class in o ' students the text to understand and understanding skill formation and development issues today's of the day current issues one is considered The world education in the system start ' drink class to the students , their from the sciences good to their mastery separately attention is given In particular , in our country too this about good o ' changes done is increasing . School of students knowledge assessment , education quality increase in order to our government by international in studies participation reach set it was put Our republic education in institutions intellectual developed person maturity find material - technical base was created , legal - me'ory documents work released

Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Actions in the strategy " Independent thoughtful , firm vital point of view look have , to the Motherland loyal young people education , democratic reforms deepening and citizenship society development in the process their social activity increase " first priority tasks as set given And this initial classes literary in education high to efficiency to achieve the ground creates

In this of teachers task initial class in their students to be studied works from each other distinction , of the writer vital events where , when statement How did he do it ? tools using reflection How did he make it ? literary heroes that he created understanding , work of heroes behavior own attitude let them know evaluate get and belongs to conclusion release skills formation it is necessary

These skills formation for initial class reading in textbooks space concept is also important of the elements one is considered The work in the plot events of the chain rings organize doer events certain one in space face will give . The concept of " space ". literary work events happen will be sure space , place (city , village , mountain , fortress such as); Literary of the work space in life

there is geographical regions (for example , Karshi , Tashkent, Nukus , Kokan , Bukhara and hz .) to be with together of the writer himself thinking found to have tissue place names as well can For example , the beginning class reading in the narration of Abu Ali Ibn Sina in his textbook Bukhara the province is exactly the same in life there is geographical area " Friendship has a lot to say Ekan » Uzbek people in a fairy tale work events one in the village , " Chicken with in the parable of the fox while events in the forest happen which was .[2.30] To the place circle concepts break down through in students Homeland feeling for the motherland faith , patriotism , humanitarianism and feelings of kindness form them own people and of his homeland loyal their children being growing up important role plays

Also new initial class in our textbook many works realistic works is considered That is in this work events sure in space happen will be An example as a 2nd grade study in the textbook " Mother Homeland in the bosom happy in the generation » section of Uzbekistan ancient cities , regions about interesting data given , exercise in the notebook while this cities about different different assignments given , ancient , famous of the regions photos cause passed .

Artistic work on work complicated process being teacher reading of classes educational duties artistic of the work to himself special features and of students readiness account to get requirement does Artistic in the work all components mutually connected will be In the work images developed goes Events developed increasingly of heroes new-new sides open goes These are the features work on at work him whole reading , perception to achieve , that is synthesis Demand does The work from the beginning until the end from being read after analysis will be done , then again high good quality to synthesis will be passed . The work to study from entering before students artistic the work to study preparation must will be So , preparation period - synthesis-analysis-synthesis process will give . Students work content right perception reach for life about known to the imagination have to be necessary Of this for preparation works will be held .

So , the beginning in classes space about concepts to explain preparation from work start need Preparation of work educational forms different is a teacher work content and to the circumstances looking the work type chooses Preparation during what are about information to give the goal done if so , first of all , of the students from themselves they are about what they know asking is determined .

For example , " Uzbek national " craftsmanship " work to study in preparation of students initial knowledge as follows defined as :

Teacher : - Today we are Uzbek national to craftsmanship travel we do Our journey of our country different different in cities will be Travelers two to the group is divided . Of this for each one group to himself given questions done , to the podium rise necessary

For group 1 questions :

- 1. In our country own craft with famous has been from artisans who do you know*
- 2. Your city which craft with famous ?*
- 3. Tashkent, Rishton , Karshi cities their own which trades with famous ?*

Same for group 2 kind of questions is given or each both group for that's it questions given , "Who first to the podium reached will go ?" condition is placed . To Khattakhta historical places described pictures , crafts from work samples hanging is placed .

To the students space concept of formation again one the method is excursions . This is work from the type nature to the image dedicated or work output , construction , city , village to life , profession circle topics and historical works when studied use can For example , " Island " in the

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3rd grade , " Uzbek" in the 2nd grade national such as " craftsmanship " . topics from learning before excursion to do to the goal according to Excursion of students in the work expression done events sure and conscious to their mastery help gives knowledge deepens , historical places , cities and they are about sure concepts forms . Excursion in children mother Homeland love wakes him up to love and save feeling educates . Work release enterprises , museum and another to places excursions while historical of events right perception that they can provides adults work with introduces the reader to labor love wakes up , to the profession directs .

Film screening to do Historical materials , places , works the author his life from learning before the movie screening if done , the students the work perception to do activates . Movie students the work to study preparation during is used . For example , 2nd grade study in the textbook " Abu Ali Ibn Sina " in his narration events Bukhara in the province being will pass , in this first of all , to the students Bukhara province about interesting the facts it is said and there is attention attraction will be done . From this then information technologies tool through that's it place visually showing more more information giving transition it is necessary Then students work where happen what is happening , how city or district they feel that Not only that the work good to understand help gives , perhaps Homeland love , him love , respect , own Homeland with pride , self country to history interest increases . [2.30] Also , students imagination to do , their understanding to clarify , conscious reading and emotional perception to reach help will give . At the students' film screening born some to the questions their themselves new student from the works answer they find Preparation their work such organize of students to study has been interests to increase service does

Summary by doing that's it to say maybe the student 's time with breath activation , mental of the world complication methodology science to the front artistic work on work ways enrichment and expand demand is putting Har one teacher the text on at work mother that's it from requirements come came out without , more search and the student received knowledge in life apply take for competence have person as formation it is necessary

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